

immerse

INTEGRATION MAPPING OF REFUGEE
AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

IMMERSE D7-6_VA

IMMERSE DELIVERABLE D7.6

Child Safeguarding Policy

Contract No: 822536

Summary

The deliverable “Child Safeguarding Policy” develops the policy and procedures applied in the IMMERSE project to ensure Children’s safety.

Authors

ZABALA Innovation Consulting

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Child Safeguard Policy

Executive summary

IMMERSE aims to enhance the socio-educative inclusion of all refugee and migrant children through the generation of new data and policy recommendations on the integration of refugee and migrant children. The project, starting in December 2018, will carry out research activities in order to create a dashboard of socio-educational indicators that will allow collecting information to be analysed and become practical policy recommendations. To achieve this goal, project partners will follow a whole school approach implementing co-creation methods to involve all the key actors in the implementation of the project.

Due to the involvement of direct contact with children it is of paramount importance the implementation of a “Child Safeguard Policy” during the project execution in order to **safeguard children’s’ rights at all times**.

This deliverable provides the IMMERSE “Child Safeguard Policy” which gathers the purpose of this Policy, the guiding principles we adhere to, and establishes internal measures to prevent and respond to child abuse for ensuring child safeguarding during the execution of the project.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and overall approach

The aim of IMMERSE “Child Safeguard Policy” is to provide guidelines for project partners to meet their responsibilities for safeguarding children during the execution of IMMERSE activities. This policy will ensure that children at IMMERSE are part of a safe, secure and caring environment, and that any suspected or actual abuse is dealt with as speedily and efficiently as possible to safeguard the best interest of the children involved.

This policy is approved by the IMMERSE General Assembly and applies to all the staff involved in the execution of the project (staff from the partner organizations and any expert professional working in the project activities) who are required to adhere to. Managers have specific responsibility for overseeing the implementation of the policy and thus for ensuring the safety of children at all times.

The specific objectives of the “Child Safeguard Policy” are summarized as follows:

- To minimise the risks of child abuse;
- To define responsibilities;
- To define a code of conduct;
- To defined procedures if concerns develop;
- To ensure both upward and downward accountability of the “Child Safeguard Policy”.

To achieve so, this document summarises all the required knowledge and procedures regarding potential risks, rules, procedures and reporting to address the following key issues (Keeping Children Safe, 2014):

- where, when and how the project affects children and what risks this presents;
- what procedures are needed to prevent harm and how to respond to concerns appropriately;
- who is the appropriate designated person/s to act as the focal point in the project to receive and manage any safeguarding concerns and subsequent inquiry/investigation;
- a clear code of conduct so that all staff understand their professional boundaries when working with children and what is and is not acceptable behaviour.

This policy is based on the [UN Convention on the Rights of the Child \(UNCRC\)](#), on the [“Ten principles for integrated child protection systems”](#) presented for discussion in the 2015 European forum on the rights of the child; and on the “Keeping Children Safe Standards and Procedures” developed by [Keeping Children Safe](#).

1.2 Definitions of harm

Definitions of “child”, “child abuse” or “child maltreatment” may differ depending on the country and their cultural understandings. Therefore, IMMERSE Child Safeguard Policy’s measures and procedures must work and adhere to the different countries and local contexts involved in the project. IMMERSE Child Safeguard Policy aims to ensure that all project partners and collaborators are clear on the definition of children and abuse and what is meant by harm to children.

IMMERSE project partners and collaborators need to be clear that ‘children’ are defined as anyone less than 18 years of age, as defined by the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), and that “abuse” is the range of acts, intentional or otherwise, which harm children (Keeping Children Safe, 2014).

Due to the difficulty to **define “harm” to children** since children can be abused in many ways depending on the context and culture, we will adhere to the definitions provided by Keeping Children Safe’s Child Safeguarding Standards (2014):

DEFINITIONS OF HARM	
PHYSICAL ABUSE	Actual or potential physical harm perpetrated by another person, adult or child. It may involve hitting, shaking, poisoning, drowning and burning. Physical harm may also be caused when a parent or carer fabricates the symptoms of, or deliberately induces illness in a child.
SEXUAL ABUSE	Forcing or enticing a child to take part in sexual activities that he or she does not fully understand and has little choice in consenting to. This may include, but is not limited to, rape, oral sex, penetration, or non-penetrative acts such as masturbation, kissing, rubbing and touching. It may also include involving children in looking at, or producing sexual images, watching sexual activities and encouraging children to behave in sexually inappropriate ways.
CHILD SEXUAL EXPLOITATION	A form of sexual abuse that involves children being engaged in any sexual activity in exchange for money, gifts, food, accommodation, affection, status, or anything else that they or their family needs. It usually involves a child being manipulated or coerced, which may involve befriending children, gaining their trust, and subjecting them to drugs and alcohol. The abusive relationship between victim and perpetrator involves an imbalance of power where the victim’s options are limited. It is a form of abuse that can be misunderstood by children and adults as consensual.
NEGLECT AND NEGLIGENT TREATMENT	Allowing for context, resources and circumstances, neglect and negligent treatment refers to a persistent failure to meet a child’s basic physical and/or psychological needs, which is likely to result in serious impairment of a child’s healthy physical, spiritual, moral and mental development. It includes the failure to properly supervise and protect children from harm and provide for nutrition, shelter and safe living/working conditions. It may also involve maternal neglect during pregnancy as a result of drug or alcohol misuse and the neglect and ill treatment of a disabled child.
EMOTIONAL ABUSE	Persistent emotional maltreatment that impacts on a child’s emotional development. Emotionally abusive acts include restriction of movement, degrading, humiliating, bullying (including cyber bullying), and threatening, scaring, discriminating, ridiculing or other non-physical forms of hostile or rejecting treatment.
COMMERCIAL EXPLOITATION	Exploiting a child in work or other activities for the benefit of others and to the detriment of the child’s physical or mental health, education, moral or social-emotional development. It includes, but is not limited to, child labour.

Table 1. Definitions of harm (Source: Keeping Children Safe, 2014)

2 Policy principles

IMMERSE consortium does not tolerate child abuse of any form by anyone who works for or is collaborating with the project and we are **committed to ensuring** that **effective action** is taken in response to any report of abuse by supporting, assisting and protecting the child involved.

IMMERSE commitment to child safeguarding is guided by the following principles:

IMMERSE POLICY PRINCIPLES	
1	All children have equal rights to protection from harm , regardless of their ethnicity, gender, age, religion or disability, or sexual orientation.
2	All staff at IMMERSE are aware of the existence of, and problems caused by, child abuse; the risks that child abuse poses to children; and how to respond appropriately when concerns arise.
3	Everyone has a responsibility to support the protection of children. All staff at IMMERSE have a duty of care to children with whom they work, are in contact with, or who are affected by their work and operations.
4	All actions on child safeguarding are taken in the best interests of the child , which are paramount. When there is a conflict of interest, the needs of the child are always paramount.
5	All matters raised and dealt with under this Policy will be kept as confidential as possible (with information being shared exclusively on a need-to-know basis), ensuring the safety of all involved (survivors, alleged perpetrators and reporters).
6	The ultimate responsibility for ensuring the safety of children rests with the general assembly and the project coordinator.

Table 2. IMMERSE Child Safeguarding Policy principles (Source: Keeping Children Safe, 2014)

ALL PARTNERS AND STAFF OF IMMERSE must commit to and uphold the principles of this Policy.

3 Problem definition

The main objective of IMMERSE is to define a new integrated methodology to generate and monitor quantitative and qualitative data and to develop a set of recommendations on the integration of refugees and migrant children in Europe.

To achieve so, IMMERSE will involve **interacting with children and the most relevant stakeholders** to identify the key parameters related to intercultural competences, wellbeing and gender affecting children's integration and to co-create a new dashboard of social and educational integration indicators.

Therefore, **one of the main challenges of the project will be the involvement of migrant children into the whole process**, not only to incorporate their needs and expectations through collaborative workshops, but as validators and active actors in IMMERSE. A **Children's Research Advisory Group (CRAG)** will be established within IMMERSE to provide advice on the development of data collection instruments, data analysis and dissemination.

A “child” is **anyone under the age of 18**, as defined by the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). This project focuses on age group between **6–18 years**: young children (6-10) and young adolescents (10–18), referred to as “adolescents” –who, as children, are entitled to protection under the UNCRC. The two age groups together are referred to in this proposal as “refugee and migrant children”. This range of age consider compulsory education in most countries (6-16) and beyond in order to include unaccompanied minors (UAMs) who are mainly aged 15-18.

It is therefore of paramount importance the implementation of a “Child Safeguard Policy” during the project execution in order to **safeguard children’s’ rights at all times**.

POTENTIAL RISK ACTIVITIES

In the following table we provide the project tasks that may present potential risk due to direct contact with children.

1.3.	RESEARCH ON INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCES AND MULTILINGUISM
Partners involved	Leader: <u>Comillas</u> ; Participants: UCC, SCIT, DOZ, ACE, MEYSS, PANTEION, RDSPEC
Objective	To identify and extract key parameters related to intercultural competences and multilingualism, in order to refine existing integration indicators. Three key issues have been identified in the literature review: language skills, intercultural awareness and empathy and cultural values. These three issues will be subjected to discussion among the different stakeholders within the three levels of the integration process: micro, meso and macro. Direct contact with children will occur at micro level which involves interaction with migrant and refugee minors, and their families. Four workshops will be organized in each country with children, split by age group (6-9, 10-12, 13-16, 17-18) and one with their families. These workshops will take place in Spain and Italy during M05-M12 .
1.4.	RESEARCH ON PSYCHOSOCIAL AND WELLBEING (M05-M12)
Partners involved	Leader: UCC; Participants: Comillas, SCIT, DOZ, ACE, MEYSS, PANTEION, RDSPEC
Objective	To identify and extract key parameters related to the children’s psychosocial wellbeing, in order to refine existing integration indicators. Three key issues have been identified in the literature: psychopathological symptoms, secure family environment and social relationships with peers. These three issues will be subject to discussion among the different stakeholders within the three levels of the integration process: micro, meso and macro. Furthermore, qualitative research techniques will be used to refine the integration indicators through the psycho-social lens under the three proposed levels described in previous task (1.3). Direct contact with children will occur at micro level which involves interaction with migrant and refugee minors, and their families. Four workshops will be organized in each country with children, split by age group (6-9, 10-12, 13-16, 17-18) and one with their families. These workshops will take place in Ireland and Greece during M05-M12 .
1.5	RESEARCH ON GENDER ISSUES (M05-M12)
Partners involved	Leader: <u>DOZ</u> ; Participants: COMILLAS, UCC, SCIT, ACE, PANTEION
Objective	To identify and extract key parameters related to gender perspective, in order to refine existing integration indicators. Three key issues have been identified in the literature review: Perceived identities, concrete grounds of gender discrimination and equity policies and strategies. These three issues will be subject to discussion with the different stakeholders within the three levels of the integration process: micro, meso and macro. Furthermore, qualitative research techniques will be used to refine the integration indicators through the gender lens under the three proposed levels. Direct contact with children will occur at micro level which involves interaction with migrant and refugee minors, and their families. Four workshops will be organized in each country with children, split by age group (6-9, 10-12, 13-16) and one with their families. These workshops will take place in Belgium and Germany during M05-M12 .
3.2	INSTRUMENTS FOR DATA COLLECTION IN SCHOOLS, NON-FORMAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENTS AND MIGRANT RECEPTION CENTRES (M15-M18)
Partners involved	Leader: <u>UCC</u> ; Participants: ALL

Objective	To define the instruments of data collection data with schools, migrant reception centres and other non-formal educational environments considering the specificity of each country where the research will be conducted. Proposed data collection instruments will be reviewed and validated by the International Advisory Group of IMMERSE and by Children’s Research Advisory Group described in WP5 (T5.6). This will ensure their appropriateness for data collection with children, guarantee that they are child-friendly and incorporate children’s voices into the process.
3.3	DATA COLLECTION IN SCHOOLS, NON-FORMAL EDUCATION ENVIRONMENTS AND MIGRANT RECEPTION CENTRES AT NATIONAL LEVEL (M18-M42)
Partners involved	<u>Leader:</u> UCC; <u>Participants:</u> Comillas; UCC, SCIT, DOZ, ACE, MEYSS, PANTEION, RDSPEC
Objective	To collect data in schools and non-formal educational centres in the six countries identified in IMMERSE: Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy and Spain . Through the questionnaire constructed in task 3.2 and by using the ICT tool deployed in WP2, data collection will be carried out by the research partners. Data will be gathered in two different phases in order to allow interim analysis during the lifetime of the project. Embeds scope for refinement of methods, instruments, integration indicators and the scope of IMMERSE, should be identified as necessary. Each partner involved in this task will use its network of associations to access to the data sources.

Table 3. IMMERSE project tasks that may present potential risk to children

In section 4.1.2 we provide a detailed *Risk Assessment* which identifies the risks that IMMERSE project may expose children to and the mitigation strategies established to reduce those risks.

4 Implementation of the policy

4.1 Awareness and prevention

4.1.1 Awareness

ACCEPTANCE AND SIGNATURE

The Child Safeguarding Policy, together with the Reporting Procedure and the Code of Conduct as well as national legislation regarding abuse, is to be made available not only to the staff from IMMERSE project partners and its volunteers, but also to all other interested parties (institutions, family members, guardians, community representatives, etc) so that IMMERSE’s approach to problems of abuse is made very clear.

The staff of IMMERSE project (partners representatives, all employed persons and volunteers) **must sign the Declaration of Acceptance of the Child Safeguarding Policy, which includes the Code of Conduct (Annex 1).**

ADHERENCE TO CODE OF CONDUCT

IMMERSE project consortium has developed a Code of Conduct which is an integral part of this policy. It applies to (and is signed by) all staff and collaborators of IMMERSE. This behaviour code outlines the conduct expected of the staff from IMMERSE project partners, and staff from other organisations who engage with children and young people through the aforementioned project and its activities.

Following this code will help to protect children from abuse and inappropriate behaviour from adults. It will also help staff to maintain the standard of behaviour expected of them and will reduce the possibility of unfounded allegations of abuse being made against them.

All members of staff are expected to report any breaches of this code to **Fr. David Holdcroft** (External Ethical Advisor of the IMMERSE project) under the whistle-blowing procedure¹ or, if necessary, under child protection procedures.

Staff who breach this code of behaviour may be subject to IMMERSE disciplinary procedures. Any breach of the code involving a member of staff from another agency may result in them being asked to leave the project. Serious breaches may also result in a referral being made to a statutory agency such as the police, the local authority children's social care department and/or the Independent Safeguarding Authority.

IMMERSE project consortium welcomes and encourages parental involvement. Parents and carers are regarded as valuable partners in promoting positive behaviour and will be involved as appropriate.

IMMERSE CODE OF CONDUCT

When working with children and young people for IMMERSE all staff are acting in a position of trust. It is important that staff is aware that they may be seen as role models by children and young people and must act in an appropriate manner at all times.

When working with children and young people, **IT IS IMPORTANT TO:**

- ✓ Follow IMMERSE's Child Safeguard Policy and procedures at all times.
- ✓ Listen to and respect children at all times.
- ✓ Avoid favouritism.
- ✓ Treat children and young people fairly and without prejudice or discrimination.
- ✓ Ensure any contact with children and young people is appropriate and in relation to the work of the project.
- ✓ Always ensure language is appropriate and not offensive or discriminatory.
- ✓ Always ensure equipment is used safely and for its intended purpose.
- ✓ Provide examples of good conduct you wish children and young people to follow.
- ✓ Challenge unacceptable behaviour and report all allegations/suspensions of abuse.
- ✓ Ensure that whenever possible, there is more than one adult present during activities with children and young people or if this is not possible, that you are within sight or hearing of other adults.
- ✓ Be close to where others are working. If a child specifically asks for or needs some private time with you, ensure other staff should know where you and the child are.
- ✓ Respect a young person's right to personal privacy.
- ✓ Encourage young people and adults to feel comfortable and caring enough to point out attitudes or behaviour they do not like.
- ✓ Recognise that special caution is required when you are discussing sensitive issues with

When working with children and young people, **YOU MUST NOT:**

¹ Whistleblowing is the term used when a worker passes on information concerning wrongdoing

- ✘ Patronise or treat children and young people as if they are silly.
- ✘ Allow allegations to go unreported.
- ✘ Develop inappropriate relationships such as contact with children and young people that is not a part of the work of IMMERSE or agreed with the manager or leader.
- ✘ Conduct a sexual relationship with a child or young person or indulge in any form of sexual contact with a child or young person. Any such behaviour between an adult member of staff and a child or young person using the services of the project represents a serious breach of trust on the part of the staff member and is not acceptable under any circumstances.
- ✘ Let children and young people have your personal contact details.
- ✘ Make sarcastic, insensitive, derogatory or sexually suggestive comments or gestures to or in front of children and young people.
- ✘ Act in a way that can be perceived as threatening or intrusive.
- ✘ Make inappropriate promises to children and young people, particularly in relation to confidentiality.
- ✘ Jump to conclusions about others without checking facts.
- ✘ Either exaggerate or trivialise child abuse issues.
- ✘ Rely on your reputation or that of the organisation to protect you.

RESPONSIBILITIES

Everyone within the project must know how to keep children safe and have appropriate learning opportunities to **develop and maintain the necessary attitudes, skills and knowledge to keep children safe**. **Children and families** should understand these commitments to child safeguarding and what to do if concerns arise.

IMMERSE project places clear responsibilities and expectations on its partners and supports them to understand and act in line with these. To achieve so, key staff will be designated at different levels with clearly defined roles and responsibilities.

As the External Ethics Advisor of the project, **Fr. David Holdcroft** will be the designated person responsible for making sure that the child safeguarding measures are integrated throughout the execution of the project and acts as a focal point.

The child safeguarding focal point is important, but that role is not responsible for making child safeguarding happen during the project. Everybody has full responsibility to implement child safeguarding measures and to carry out their respective roles on child safeguarding.

LEVELS OF RESPONSIBILITY	
ALL	Everybody has responsibility for child safeguarding.
	Become familiar with the child safeguarding policy.
	Be aware of abuse and risks to children.
	Abide by the Code of Conduct.
	Be vigilant.
	Prevent abuse/ protect children.
	Report concerns.
	Promote good practice & challenge poor practice.
	Display and encourage an open/aware culture for all.

	Children are informed of complaints procedures and how to report any concerns/misconduct.
ZABALA	Ensure child safeguarding policy is implemented.
	Enforce Code of Conduct and monitor adherence to it.
	Oversee the implementation of the child safeguarding policy and regularly monitor implementation.
	Managing all aspects of reporting and responding to incidents.
ZABALA / External Ethical advisor	Address staff concerns around child safeguarding.
	Overall coordination of safeguarding developments.

Table 4. Levels of responsibility at IMMERSE project

4.1.2 Prevention

SAFER RECRUITMENT PROCEDURES

The recruitment and selection of staff for the project, must reflect IMMERSE's commitment to the safeguarding of children, ensuring that the necessary checks and procedures, especially criminal records checks following the national law, are in place to prevent anyone unsuitable from working with children.

Contractors are required to sign a Self-declaration regarding offences involving minors (Annex 3). Also, successful candidates are informed of the binding nature of this Policy, the relative Reporting Procedure and the Code of Conduct, and of the fact that the principles contained in these documents must be adhered to in both the professional and private life of the person.

DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS RAISING

IMMERSE ensures that the Policy, the Reporting Procedure and the Code of Conduct are disseminated, promoted and distributed broadly among project partners and staff of the project as well as among stakeholders at micro, meso and macro level, including children and those who look after them.

The dissemination is carried in an appropriate manner in order to ensure that the Policy and the Code of Conduct are distributed widely and fully understood. This may involve translations into the languages of beneficiaries and the production of child-friendly material.

RISK ASSESSMENT

ZABALA as part of IMMERSE consortium has developed a Risk Assessment as an integral part of this policy which identifies the risks the project may expose children to and the mitigation strategies established to reduce those risks.

This assessment has been conducted according to the risk assessment procedure developed by Keeping Children Safe (2014) which involves:

- Identification of risks. Detecting the potential risk that will have an impact on children.
- Assessing the nature of risks in terms of likelihood they could occur and the seriousness of the impact on children.
 - **High.** Highly likely to happen and significant impact on child;
 - **Medium.** Either highly likely to happen or significant impact on child;
 - **Low.** Less likely to happen and less of an impact on child.
- Mitigation strategy. Implemented strategies to minimize and prevent risk, reducing the likelihood of harm and abuse from actually occurring;

- Clearly assigning responsibilities in the mitigation strategy;
- Reviewing risks and mitigation strategies, especially when conditions/contexts change.

Area of risk	Potential risk	Risk assessment	Mitigation strategy	Actions to implement
Staff	Informal process for recruiting staff, no reference checks	Medium	Prevention measures - Safer recruitment procedure	Staff are required to sign a Self-declaration regarding offences involving minors (Annex 3)
	Staff not aware or trained	Medium	Prevention measures - Dissemination and awareness raising	Staff are required to sign the Policy, Reporting Procedure and Code of Conduct Staff will receive, if possible, induction and training regarding the Policy and the Reporting Procedure
	Staff who do harm children	Medium	Prevention measures - Safer recruitment procedure	Staff are required to sign a Self-declaration regarding offences involving minors (Annex 3)
			Prevention measures - Dissemination and awareness raising among staff	Staff are required to sign the Policy, Reporting Procedure and Code of Conduct Staff will receive, if possible, induction and training regarding the Policy and the Reporting Procedure
			Prevention measures - Dissemination and awareness raising among children and their families	Children are informed of complaints procedures and how to report any concern/misconduct
			Reporting Procedure	Appropriate process for reporting and responding to child protection incidents/concerns that provides clear steps to take when concern/incident arise
ICT	Disclosure of children personal data	Medium	Compliance with GDPR 2016/679 (ethics deliverables D8.1 and D8.3)	IT systems are monitored to ensure usage does not breach the child safeguarding policy
	Inappropriate use of children images	Medium	Compliance with GDPR 2016/679.	Checking that images of children do not breach the child safeguarding policy
			Rules for the use of images of children integrated in child safeguarding policy.	
COMMUNITY	Abuse arising within the community	Medium	IMMERSE acquires responsibility to report on suspected abuse	Reported to the formal authorities or to organisations able to deal with cases appropriately

Table 5. IMMERSE Risk Assessment table

STAFF RISKS

One of the main risks for children during IMMERSE project is staff who do harm children, whether deliberately or through a lack of understanding of what constitutes abusive behaviour.

To reduce this risk, IMMERSE makes totally clear through the binding nature of this Policy, the Codes of Conduct, the safer recruitment procedures, training and internal communications that child abuse by staff and volunteers will not be tolerated.

IMMERSE also extends this obligation to keep children safe to their conduct towards children with whom they have contact, outside the work environment as well as inside.

COMMUNITY RISKS

Abuse arising within the community may not be due to IMMERSE project. However, IMMERSE acquires responsibility to report on suspected or actual child abuse taking place.

This will be reported to the formal authorities or, where they are weak or corrupt, to organisations able to deal with cases appropriately. The reporting process will be decided at a local level in order to ensure that children and their families are not put at further risk or made vulnerable by the very action of reporting harm and/or abuse.

ICT RISKS

The main ICT risk for children identified for the IMMERSE project are the risks coming from the processing of personal data, including the **disclosure of children personal data**, making them identifiable, and the improper use of their image.

In order to avoid this risk, IMMERSE project partners will carefully follow the data protection procedures established in the GDPR 2016/679 and fully explained in the ethics requirements deliverables of the IMMERSE project (D8.1 and D8.3).

In addition, all partners and staff of IMMERSE are committed to the following procedure regarding data protection:

- When collecting and using of children personal data for research purposes, special care will be taken to guarantee the protection of minor's fundamental rights and freedom such as privacy;
- Consideration of country and institutional-specific ethical regulations and child protection policies during data collection and data storage phase;
- Information about the project purposes and methods, data to be collected and policies adopted to protect children privacy will be provided to participants together with an informed consent that will be requested to be signed prior to project participation by any participant;
- Regarding minors' participation, approval from their parents or legally authorised representatives will be required.

In addition, IMMERSE project partners will ensure **good practice when using images** (photographs, video or social media) of children by following the rules below (Keeping Children Safe, 2014):

- Images of children must not show them in states of undress or in inappropriate poses;
- Details attached to images and included in stories must not allow that child to be traced to his or her home or community;
- Distinctive buildings, street signs or landmarks should not be included in an image if they identify where a child lives or works;
- Geotagging of images should be disabled when taking photographs;
- Ensure the photographer/journalist/translator we have employed has been properly vetted and reference checked;
- Make sure you have been given permission by children and their parents/carers to take their image and use their information.

4.2 Reporting procedure

Even with all the preventive measures detailed above, child abuse may still happen during the project. It is crucial that in these cases, a solid reporting procedure is in place to respond in an appropriate, effective and timely manner, in line with the principles set out in this Policy and Code of Conduct, ensuring no further harm to the child.

It is **compulsory** for all IMMERSE staff to internally report **witnessed, suspected or alleged cases** of:

- Child abuse or exploitation by another staff member, partners or contractors, as well any external person outside the project;
- Breaches of the Policy or Code of Conduct by another staff member, partner or contractor, as well as any external person outside the project.

During the reporting process, IMMERSE ensures the following commitments:

- the guiding principle is to ensuring the safety, wellbeing, dignity and the best interest of the child involved in the reporting procedure;
- any allegation or concern regarding the abuse of a child must be treated seriously, ensuring that all parties are treated fairly, and procedures are transparent and in line with the law;
- particular care should be taken in regard to confidentiality and the sharing of information with appropriate people, bearing in mind the protection of the child, the reporter and the alleged perpetrator.

The following Reporting Procedure flowchart provides the detailed guidance on how to report and who to report to during IMMERSE project. This procedure, as well as the Policy and the Code of Conduct, must be signed by IMMERSE staff and is also distributed among stakeholders, including children and their families, so everyone is clear about what steps to take regarding the safety of children and other witnesses during IMMERSE project.

Figure 1: IMMENSE Reporting Procedure. Source: Child Safeguarding Standards, Keep Children Safe (2014)

5 Accountability

IMMERSE project's Child Safeguard Policy and procedures will be regularly monitored in order to track progress and performance on child safeguarding and to ensure both upward and downward accountability, including information on safeguarding issues and child protection cases, as well as obtain lessons learnt that will be reported to key stakeholders.

Active monitoring involves regular checking to ensure that safeguards are working and how the systems and processes are working to prevent the risk of abuse. To achieve so, surveys or interviews with staff on how effective the policy is and what needs improving will be conducted annually. **Reactive monitoring** involves learning from mistakes. Good case management will provide a valuable insight into why the abuse took place and whether the organisation could have done anything, to prevent it.

6 Bibliography

Child Safeguarding Standards and how to implement them, Keeping Children Safe. Available [here](#)

Principles for integrated child protection systems, European Commission. Available [here](#)

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, United Nations. Available [here](#)

7 Annexes

1. Declaration of Acceptance of the Policy, Code of Conduct and Reporting Procedure by the partner organizations and staff of IMMERSE.
2. Self-declaration regarding offences involving minors.
3. Report Form

ANNEX 1

IMMERSE Declaration of acceptance

I confirm that I have received and read, and, therefore, AGREED TO SIGN for the entire duration of my collaboration with IMMERSE (or participation carried out by one of its partner organisations):

- the Child Safeguarding Policy and the Code of Conduct,
- the General Reporting Procedure for Child Safeguarding.

I also acknowledge that the contents of those documents may be added to or altered at any time at its absolute discretion by IMMERSE Consortium. To this effect I declare and warrant to accept as of now unconditionally any such changes and additions and to add here to them.

Should I fail to do so, I acknowledge and accept that IMMERSE Consortium may terminate whatever relationship they have with me, without warning or discussion.

Name and Surname: _____

Position held and project/activity:

City: _____

Legible signature: _____

Date: _____

ANNEX 2

IMMERSE Self-declaration regarding offences involving minors

Given that:

1. The candidates that IMMERSE CONSORTIUM looks for and selects, directly or through its partners, for any kind of positions/qualification may be involved in direct contact with children, either individually or in groups, in one-to-one contacts without any kind of supervision, or in the management of programmes which involve direct support for children;
2. it is indispensable that candidates have irreproachable conduct, in particular in their relations with children as required by IMMERSE's Child Safeguarding Policy.

The undersigned _____ born in _____
on _____ Fiscal Code _____ resident
in _____ identity document _____ n. _____
issued by _____ issue date _____

as **employee** or: **collaborator** **volunteer** **trainee**

of IMMERSE'S PARTNER or a partner organisation carrying out a project/activity for IMMERSE'S PARTNER in the project/activity:

fully aware of the importance of the information I provide in this document to IMMERSE'S PARTNER and of the legal consequences, both civil and criminal, I may face if I provide false information or make wilful omissions in accordance with Art. 76 DPR 445/2000 or Art. 640 of the Criminal Code², and that any such false information or wilful omissions are in themselves

² This template makes reference to the Italian law, but each pilot will make reference to its local or/and national law

just cause to terminate the contract in accordance with Art. 2119 of the Civil Code in the most serious cases,

DECLARE AND WARRANT

under my own responsibility, with specific reference to offences involving minors

1. that I do not have any criminal proceedings pending
2. that I have never been found guilty of a criminal offence, even if it was not enforced (because of a pardon, amnesty, remission of the penalty or judicial pardon)
3. that I am not aware of any criminal investigations in which I am involved
4. that I have never been charged with or under investigation for any offence, including judgements that were not enforced or offences that came under the statute of limitations

Moreover, I **will immediately inform** IMMERSE'S PARTNER if **any change whatever** occurs with regards to the above declarations.

Place and date

Legible signature of the person making the self-declaration

ANNEX 3

IMMERSE Report Form

CONFIDENTIAL

Programme/Place:

Name and Surname of the child:

Details of the report:

Date: _____ Times: _____

Place:

Details of the person making the report:

Name and surname:

Address:

Main telephone no.:

Secondary telephone no.:

Occupation:

Relationship to the child:

Details of the child:

Name and surname:

Age:

Date of Birth:

Gender:

Address:

Reception facilities:

School:

Class: _____ Teacher: _____

Nationality:

Language spoken:

Religion: _____

Disability (if "yes" please provide details): _____

Identity card no.: _____

Person responsible/guardian: _____

Recent changes in the child's behaviour:

Details of the alleged abuse: who, what, where and when
(include the testimony of the victim if possible)

Details of the suspected perpetrator (if known):

Name and surname: _____

Address: _____

Age: _____

Date of birth: _____

Occupation: _____

Type of work: _____

Relationship to the child: _____

Presumed current whereabouts of the suspect: _____

Present safety of the child (include information regarding whether the place in which s/he is staying is safe, whether there are risks of any kind, whether s/he has expressed any fears that should be considered etc)

Was emergency medical treatment requested for the child?

If "yes", please indicate who the request was made to (service, names of staff and contact details) and whether treatment has already been given (where, which service, names of staff and contact details):

Who else knows about the case?

Agency, body, organisation or other:

Member of the family or others (please specify):

Action taken so far (e.g. case reported to the judicial authorities, the social services, other.

Please specify place and date, action taken, persons involved and their contact details)

Complaint details provided by:

(if it is the same person who made the complaint, there is no need to fill in this box)

Name:

Role and place:

Date:

Signature:

THIS SECTION IS TO BE FILLED IN BY THE LINE MANAGER WHO RECEIVED THE REPORT

Name: _____

Position: _____

Place: _____

Date and time report received:

Action taken by the line manager:

Is there any connection between the alleged abuser and IMMERSE's PARTNER or its partners?

Should the case be dealt with using external procedures, in other words, is there any connection between the case and IMMERSE's PARTNER or a partner? (Yes/No and please specify):

Should the case be dealt with using internal procedures (Yes/No and please specify):

Are any eventual decisions already taken by the line manager in line with the Policy and relative Procedure for Child Safeguarding? (please supply details)

Were the judicial authorities involved? (Yes/No, please specify why)

Were public authorities for the protection of children involved? (Yes/No, please specify why)

What other action was taken to ensure the safety of the child?

Was medical treatment requested?

Date and time the child was sent for/received medical treatment:

Signature of the line manager